

EXPERIMENTAL AND MOLECULAR DYNAMICS ANALYSIS OF ANTIMICROBIAL ADDITIVE MIGRATION FROM BIOCOMPOSITE PACKAGING

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ABSTRACT

Biomass-filled biocomposites are gaining increased acceptance and utilisation in the field of rigid packaging, especially in an atmosphere of increased environmental responsibility and sustainability. Polylactide (PLA)-based biocomposites particularly are driving this growth because of their potentially renewable and thermo-mechanically stability necessitated by packaging materials. Nano-silver at low loading levels can provide antibacterial functionality for rigid biocomposites, and assists in creating multiple-use packaging. Inclusion of heavy metal silver nanoparticles is potentially hazardous for human physiology at high concentrations, emerging from migration into food, hence requiring systematic investigation at the molecular level to deal with a diverse range of polymer and biomass blends are being developed for food packaging applications today. The current study investigates the migration of heavy metals produced through chemical reduction of heavy metals and are compounded with the bioplastics such as PLA primarily through melt-extrusion. The heavy metal migration from the biocomposites into food simulants such as alcoholic, fatty, and aqueous foods are investigated through experimental studies. Further, the migration behaviour, which is predominantly based on diffusion is studied at the molecular level using molecular dynamics tools to gain understanding of the interactions of heavy metal particles within the PLA and biocomposite molecular networks. The migration of antibacterial heavy metal additives from PLA biocomposite at 313 K and 343 K using molecular dynamics simulations was carried out. The heavy metal migration levels into food simulants was deemed to be at safe for food contact at 0.20 – 3.08 mg/kg, which meets the standard limits of 60 mg/kg and 10 mg/dm². The analyses provide data on the degree and magnitude of uncertainties related to food safety, to afford better product design and establish the potential of PLA/biomass biocomposites for food packaging applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of food packaging is to contain food in a cost-effective way that satisfies industry requirements and consumer needs, maintains food safety, and minimizes environmental impact [1]. The accurate selection of packaging materials and technologies preserves product quality and freshness during distribution and storage. Plastic packaging materials are also often contaminated by foodstuff and biological substances, hence recycling these material is unpractical and not cost-effective [2]. As a result, thousands of tons of used plastic packaging materials, are landfilled every year [3], which is an emerging crisis for example in Australia and the European Union. Growing environmental awareness has led to user-friendly and eco-friendly packaging. As a result, biodegradability is not only a functional requirement, but also an important environmental attribute. Biodegradable polymers derived from replenishable agricultural feedstock, animal sources, marine food processing industry wastes, or microbial sources are a good fit for packaging, and are driving substantial growth in this field. Biopolymer (e.g., PLA)-based packaging are now becoming commonplace in food-contact articles at retail food establishments [2].

Polylactide (PLA), the biodegradable synthetic aliphatic polyester, has been studied extensively [4] for food packaging. Based on experimental research, PLA has been found to be safe for its use in food-contact [5]. In addition, food-borne microbial outbreaks are driving a search for innovative ways to inhibit microbial growth in the foods while maintaining quality, freshness, and safety [6]. Traditional

systems are reaching their limits with regard to further extension of shelf-life of packaged food. To provide this shelf-life extension, and to improve the quality, safety and integrity of the packaged food, innovative active and intelligent packaging concepts are being developed, including oxygen, moisture, and ethylene scavengers, ethylene emitters, flavour imparting or scavenging chemicals, and antimicrobial agents for microbiological safety of food [7]. The application of antimicrobial agents to packaging can create an environment inside the package that may delay or even prevent the growth of microorganisms on the product surface and, hence, lead to an extension of the shelf life and/or the improved safety of the product. Antimicrobial packaging is a form of active packaging that interacts with the product or the headspace between the package and the food system, to obtain a desired outcome [6]. Adding nanocomposites or nanoparticles into biocomposite packaging materials [8, 9] can better protect foods by modifying the permeation behaviour of foils, deodorising, increasing barrier properties, blocking ultraviolet light, improving mechanical and heat resistance properties, and developing antimicrobial and antifungal surfaces. Silver ions in 10^{-9} – 10^{-6} mol/L concentration works through ionic exchange of Ag^+ into food/food simulant, which increases with higher acidity or ionic strength [10]. A previous analysis of food additives in fatty and alcoholic foods with polypropylene packaging [11] using a two-phase molecular diffusion coefficient elucidated the migration being a function of molecular structure, interaction energy between polymer/additive, food simulant type, and system temperature, and as expected, an elevated temperature causes a larger free volume availability, enhancing diffusion.

Diffusion of nanoparticles from rigid plastics into food and thereby into the human physiology, hence is an ever important issue in the field of active packaging. The current work analyses the diffusion of silver nanoparticles from PLA and PLA biocomposite into food simulants, using a framework adopted in Ref. [11]. Diffusion coefficient is critical in understanding specific response of active packaging in containing nanoparticle migration. Experimentally, diffusion coefficients are obtained through inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) technique.

As novel additives are developed to enhance the effectiveness of active biocomposite packaging, a concomitant increase in diverse risks to the public health ensues. To that end, computational support for enabling knowledgeable design and scalability of biocomposites becomes imperative. The molecular dynamics support in this context is valuable for a holistic design approach for biocomposite packaging with diverse range of additives. The current paper presents a study on the migration of common packaging additives as a function of concentration of food simulant and temperature in PLA biocomposites. The migration behaviour analysis is custom designed using open source molecular dynamics software to determine the diffusion behaviour, and correlated with experimental migration studies using the ICP-OES.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental Migration Testing

The migration testing for the biocomposite and filler materials was conducted according to guidelines of the European Council Directive 82/711/EEC with two food simulants, i.e., 3% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid, and 95% (v/v) aqueous ethanol. Combined, these simulants correspond to a range of alcoholic, aqueous, and acidic foods that may be in contact with the biocomposites. The migration of AgNP was established at oven temperature of 40 °C (313 K) and 70 °C (343 K). At designated intervals, the migration into the simulants was recorded, followed by analysis on a Perkin Elmer Optima 2100 DV ICP-OES spectrometer.

2.2 Molecular Dynamics Simulations

The structures for the poly-l-lactide (PLLA), ethanol, water, silver cluster, and isooctane were created on Gaussview 6.0 and Gaussian 9 and further pre-processed on Visual Molecular Dynamics (VMD 1.9.3) Molefactory plugin (Figure 1). Further, the Force field Toolkit (FFTK) [12] was used to parametrise the molecules. NAMD 2.13 [13] was used to minimise the force field to 0 K to relax the molecules to their lowest energy state, and sequentially raise the temperature of the solvation build to

343 K to observe migration through a classical mechanics approach. A single PLLA chain consisted of 5 monomer repeat units, along with silver ions. The minimum energy conformation of the 5-mer PLLA and other structures were reduced using sequential minimisation of bonds, angles, and dihedrals in the structure. CHARMM force field was applied for parametrisation, which calculates the coordinates and velocity of each atom at specified intervals isothermally.

Figure 1: The van der Waals representations of (a) 2-hydroxypropanoic acid (poly-l-lactic acid 5-mer), and (b) 2,2,4-trimethylpentane (iso-octane).

The interactions between the PLLA, iso-octane, ethanol, and water along with the silver nanoparticle are analyzed in a solvation box ($a=b=c=80 \text{ \AA}$), and subjected to temperature increases after isothermal steps, starting at 200 K.

Table 1: Molecular Dynamics Simulations Set-up

Simulation Case	Solvation box	Solvation box dimensions	Temperature
1	16 PLLA + 80 C ₂ H ₅ OH + 3 Ag + 81 H ₂ O	80 Å × 80 Å × 80 Å	313 K
2	16 PLLA + 80 C ₂ H ₅ OH + 3 Ag + 81 H ₂ O	80 Å × 80 Å × 80 Å	343 K
3	16 PLLA + 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane + 3 Ag + 81 H ₂ O	80 Å × 80 Å × 80 Å	313 K
4	16 PLLA + 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane + 3 Ag + 81 H ₂ O	80 Å × 80 Å × 80 Å	343 K

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Molecular Dynamics Analysis

The molecular dynamics analysis on the PLLA-encapsulated AgNPs are shown in Figure 2. The Ag⁺ ions showed migration from the solvation box towards outside the simulation system. The migration of charged particles is increased by a loosely bound polymer structure as with the 5-mer structure of the PLLA. This behaviour is indicative of solution cast films, where the polymerised structure is not completely consolidated as with closed systems such as injection moulding.

Figure 2: AgNP migration from the PLLA/ethanol/H₂O system.

The minimization of the energy of the solvation system was performed for 2×10^6 time steps, corresponding to a physical time of 4 ns. The energy decrease with respect to the system is shown in Figure 3. Following the energy minimization, the temperature was raised to 313 K and 343 K and the corresponding changes in the migration behavior were studied.

Figure 3: The energy minimisation of the system, showing the electrical, potential and total energies with respect to time steps.

3.2 Experimental Migration

For food packaging applications, strict regulations control the heavy metal migration limits from packaging materials. For example, the European Union legislation 2002/72/EC sets the limits of migration through guidelines in 82/711/EEC. The maximum heavy metal concentration of general substances migrating from the packaging materials in selected food simulants for a certain migration time for metals may not exceed 60 mg/kg or 10 mg/dm².

The initial Ag concentration in the antibacterial biocomposite was 46.65 mg/kg. The migration rate is calculated using Equation 1.

$$\text{Migration rate (\%)} = \frac{M [\text{food simulant}]}{M [\text{packaging}]} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The experimental migration data of AgNPs from the biocomposite are presented in Figure 4. The migration observed in aqueous acetic acid, which were 6.6% and 5.1% at 40 °C and 70 °C respectively, while in aqueous ethanol, the highest migration rates were 0.45% and 0.47% at 40 °C and 70 °C, respectively.

Figure 4: Migration rate of AgNPs in food simulants with variable temperatures.

In all cases, the calculated AgNP content in the food simulants was within the range of 0.20 – 3.08 mg/kg, which meets the European Union (EU) legislation limits of 60 mg/kg and 10 mg/dm². The food simulant, migration time, and temperature dictate the degree of silver particle migration from food packaging [44]. The overall AgNP migration was higher in 3% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid over 95% (v/v) aqueous ethanol because of the limited AgNP solubility. With an increase in temperature, the AgNP solubility in aqueous acetic acid increases as well, and hence the overall migration at 70°C is higher over 40°C. Organic additives including plasticizers and stabilizers also migrate into ethanol, lowering the solubility of AgNPs. The migration of AgNPs in food simulants is resultant of the aforementioned mechanisms. The industrial hemp crop absorbs heavy metals from soil inherently, and hence the analysis of migration of such heavy metals including Ni, Cd, Pb, and Cr is imperative for food packaging biocomposites. Table 2 shows the migrated amount of heavy metals (Ni, Cd, Pb, and Cr) from the biocomposite in food simulants at 70 °C for 48 h. The migration values of heavy metals are practically negligible, and bears no health risk to food in contact. Thus, using HH, which is loaded with heavy metals in HH/PLA biocomposite does not bear a negative effect on food safety because of high retention within the HH structure, and consequent low migration to food.

Table 2: Migration of heavy metals in acetic acid and ethanol food simulants

	Ni (mg/kg)	Cd (mg/kg)	Pb (mg/kg)	Cr (mg/kg)
Acetic Acid (3% v/v)	0.013	0.002	0.004	0.199
Ethanol (95% v/v)	0.012	0.002	0.003	0.147

Many heavy metals are capable of imparting antimicrobial activity in food packaging plastics. However, Ag-based nanoparticles are a particularly effective solution for a diverse range of plastics for this purpose. However, the main concern with the usage of nanoscale additive in plastics without encapsulation is the ready migration into foodstuffs, which causes adverse toxic effects on human physiology. The encapsulation of AgNPs in HH specifically is a way of precluding excessive nanoparticle migration into food and subsequently affect human physiology.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The experimental and molecular dynamics studies provide greater insight into the migration behaviour of active packaging additives through elucidating their interaction with the food simulants at specified temperatures. PLA-based packaging biocomposite was effective in containing the silver nanoparticles through encapsulation within the filler surface.

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